

field evaluated for yield potential and GM resistance.

Field trials led to the identification of 4 cultures (2 from CR294, 1 from CR316, 1 from CR318) of 125 to 130 d duration with high resistance to GM (see table). All cultures also possess good levels of field resistance to bacterial leaf blight. They are being tested under the All India Coordinated multilocation testing in GM problem areas. Preliminary data of 1984 kharif showed that CR294-548 (IET9233) was resistant at the three sites of high GM incidence (Mangalore, Raipur, Sakoli). Average yield was outstanding in both the three high-incidence locations and in the nine test locations.

Tailoring GM resistance by exploiting the duplicate and complementary genes from IR20 might possibly counter the increasing spectrum and admixtures of GM biotypes. $\mathcal{J}$

Sources of resistance to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) and green leafhopper (GLH)

R. Velusamy and P.C. Sundara Babu, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Coimbatore 541003, India; and D. V. Seshu, IRTP, IRR1

We evaluated 100 rice accessions received through IRWBPHN 85 for resistance to WBPH *Sogatella furcifera*. The 15 accessions identified as resistant were further evaluated for resistance to GLH *Nephotettix virescens* by the standard seedbox screening.

Pregerminated seeds were sown in 60- $\times$ 40- $\times$ 10-cm seedboxes; Ptb 33 and TN1 served as resistant and susceptible checks. Separate seedboxes were used for each hopper species. Each accession was replicated five times for each insect species.

Each seedling was infested with 8 2d-instar nymphs of WBPH and 5 2d-instar nymphs of GLH 7 d after sowing. Damage was rated when 90-100% of TN1 plants died.

All 15 accessions were resistant to WBPH and to GLH (see table). $\square$

Reaction of rice varieties, cultures, and mutants to yellow stem borer (YSB) in Kerala

S. G. Sreekumar and C. Nundakumar, College of Agriculture, Vellayani, Kerala 695522 India

Activity of the YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) was studied on 24 rice varieties, cultures, and mutants in 1984 kharif and 26 in 1985 kharif.

Entries were grown in 20-m² plots replicated 3 times. Incidence of deadhearts 45 d after transplanting and incidence of whiteheads 10 d before harvest were recorded and damage percentage was calculated.

In 1984, deadheart incidence was highest in culture 1907 and lowest in culture 4. The highest number of whiteheads was in TKM9 and the lowest in culture 52-3-6.

In 1985, the incidence of deadhearts was highest in culture 4-4 and TKM9 and lowest in culture 126. The highest number of whiteheads was recorded in culture 4-4 and the lowest in Triveni (see table). $\square$

Rice resistance to WBPH and GLH. TNAU, Coimbatore, India, 1985.

Designation	Damage rating ^a	
	WBPH	GLH
Chempan	1 a	1 a
Chempan pandi	3 b	1 a
Horonamawee	1 a	1 a
IR9852-22-3	1 a	1 a
IR13427-40-2-3-3	1 a	1 a
IR13429-1961	1 a	1 a
IR13475-7-3-2	1 a	1 a
IR15429-268-1-2-1	3 b	1 a
IR15527-21-2-3	3 b	1 a
IR15529-256-1	3 b	1 a
IR15795-151-2-3-2-2	1 a	1 a
IR28154-101-3-2	1 a	1 a
Podiwi A8	3 b	1 a
Valsara Champara	1 a	1 a
Sufaida 172	1 a	1 a
Ptb 33 (resistant check)	1 a	1 a
TN1 (susceptible check)	9 c	9 b

^aMean of 5 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

YSB incidence in rice in Kerala, India, 1984 and 1985 kharif.^a

Variety	Deadhearts (%)		Whiteheads (%)	
	1984	1985	1984	1985
Jyothi	1.0 (1.2)	0.2 (0.8)	7.3 (2.7)	5.6 (2.3)
Jaya	0.7 (1.1)	0.4 (1.0)	3.9 (1.9)	14.1 (3.8)
MO 5	0.2 (0.8)	0.1 (0.8)	6.0 (2.2)	10.0 (3.1)
MO 6	0.4 (1.0)	0.1 (0.8)	12.2 (3.5)	7.4 (2.6)
TKM 9	0.7 (1.1)	0.6 (1.0)	36.2 (5.9)	20.1 (4.5)
IR36	0.2 (0.8)	0.5 (1.0)	7.3 (2.6)	13.0 (3.6)
IR50	0.2 (0.8)	0.1 (0.8)	4.5 (2.2)	13.3 (3.5)
<i>Culture</i>				
1907	1.3 (1.3)	0.3 (0.9)	9.5 (3.1)	9.1 (3.0)
1954	0.3 (0.9)	0.2 (0.8)	4.5 (1.9)	10.5 (3.2)
43-1-4	0.2 (0.9)	0.3 (0.9)	5.5 (2.4)	10.7 (3.2)
52-3-6 ^b	0.1 (0.8)	0.4 (0.9)	2.7 (1.4)	9.7 (3.1)
25337	0.3 (0.9)	0.2 (0.8)	7.4 (2.5)	7.4 (2.6)
169 ^b	0.5 (1.0)	0.2 (0.8)	12.1 (3.5)	5.1 (2.3)
25331	0.3 (0.9)	0.3 (0.9)	9.0 (2.7)	15.2 (3.9)
4 ^b	0.1 (0.8)	0.3 (0.9)	4.6 (2.0)	13.1 (3.6)
1537/2 (Karthika)	0.2 (0.9)	0.2 (0.9)	5.2 (2.1)	7.1 (2.7)
126	0.2 (0.8)	0.0 (0.7)	10.3 (2.8)	6.3 (2.5)
26-1-1	0.2 (0.8)	0.4 (0.9)	5.8 (2.4)	9.6 (3.0)
4-4	0.2 (0.8)	0.4 (0.9)	5.7 (2.3)	20.4 (4.5)
<i>Mutant</i>				
6	0.3 (0.9)	0.3 (0.9)	17.8 (4.0)	17.8 (4.0)
210	0.2 (0.8)	0.1 (0.8)	11.5 (3.3)	12.4 (3.5)
2	0.3 (0.9)	0.2 (0.9)	13.8 (3.7)	15.0 (2.4)
102 ^b	0.4 (1.0)	0.1 (0.8)	6.6 (2.6)	5.6 (2.4)
109	0.2 (0.8)	0.3 (0.9)	9.5 (3.1)	13.7 (3.3)
Cul. 23332-2	-	0.2 (0.8)	-	13.2 (3.6)
Triveni ^b	-	0.3 (0.8)	-	5.0 (2.2)
CD at 5% level	0.2	0.2	1.3	1.2

^aFigures in parentheses are square root transformation values. ^bLess susceptible to stem borer incidence.